

Removal of basic dyes from aqueous solutions using coconut hard shell powder as a sorbent

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Abstract : The potentiality of sorbent coconut hard shell powder (CHSP) has been investigated as an effective sorbent to removal of malachite green and crystal violet from aqueous solutions. The maximum removal of malachite green and crystal violet have been found at pH 10.5 and 10.2, initial dyes concentration 5 mg L⁻¹ and temperature 30 °C, respectively. The effects of different parameters such as contact-time, particle diameter of the sorbent, dyes concentration, pH of the solution and temperature have been investigated.

Keywords : Basic dye, adsorption, coconut hard shell powder.

The disposal of the dye-house wastewater poses one of the major problems of textile industries. Such effluents contain a number of contaminants including acid or caustic, dissolved solids, toxic compounds and color. Removal of dyes and other waste materials by various adsorbent has been successfully carried out by large number of workers worldwide¹. The aim of the present work is to study the suitability of coconut hard shell powder (CHSP) to remove basic dyes from aqueous solutions and its applications as potential commercial sorbents.

Experimental

The dyes used are malachite green and crystal violet (Sandoz India Ltd.). All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Coconut hard shell powder (CHSP) was prepared in the laboratory. 500 g of coconut hard shell was treated with 500 ml of 1 M H₂SO₄. The material was repeatedly washed with distilled water and heated in oven at 150 °C for 12 h and then powdered. The powder was sieved through 175 mesh and 150 mesh and was used for all the experiments. Physical properties of CHSP are as : surface area (m² g⁻¹) 36; bulk density (g cm⁻³) 0.6082; particle size (μg) 175–150; diameter (cm) 2.14 × 10⁻²; porosity 0.36; moisture 2.50%; volatile matter 6.54%; carbon 40.80%; ash 35.16%; non-volatile oxides 15%.

In the present investigation batch mode of operation was used by shaking 1.0 g of desired coconut hard shell powder with 50 ml aqueous solution of the dyes of desired concentration (malachite green or crystal violet) at different temperatures and pH in different glass bottles in a shaking thermostat with a constant speed of 125 rpm. The pH of sorbate solution was adjusted by adding HCl or NaOH. The process of adsorption was noted at different time interval till the attainment of saturation. At the completion of predetermined time interval, the sorbate and sorbent were separated by high speed centrifugation at 20000 rpm and the supernatant liquid of malachite green and crystal violet were analysed by spectrophotometer (Spectronic-20 Baush and Lomb) at 425 and 588 nm, respectively. Blank samples were also run under similar conditions of concentration.

Results and discussion

A series of experiments were performed at different initial concentration of both the dyes at 30 °C and pH 10.2 (crystal violet) and 10.5 (malachite green). Adsorption increased rapidly in initial stages for both the dyes and become slow at later stages till the attainment of equilibrium (90 and 100 min respectively).

The rate constant for the adsorption (k_{ad} min⁻¹) for both the dyes was evaluated in the light of Lagergreen rate equation².

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log q_e - \frac{k_{ad}}{2.303} t \quad (1)$$

where q and q_e are the amounts of adsorbate (mg g^{-1}) at time t (min) and at equilibrium respectively. The linear plots of $\log (q_e - q)$ versus t suggested the first order kinetics of the uptake of both the dyes. The values of k_{ad} at different temperatures for both dyes were calculated from the slopes of these lines and are given in Table 1.

During the batch mode of operation, there is possibility of intra-particle pore diffusion of sorbate which is often the rate controlling step³. Thus, the rate constants of intra-particle diffusion (k_p) at different temperatures were determined by using Weber and Moris relationship⁴, $q = k_p t^{1/2}$, by plotting amount of the dye adsorbed versus square root of time. The value of k_p obtained from the slope of the respective plots are given in Table 1 which indicate that intra-particle diffusion can be a rate controlling step³.

This was further supported by calculating pore diffusion coefficients \bar{D} for intra-particle transport of dyes with in the adsorbent using following equations assuming spherical geometry of the adsorbent⁵.

$$t_{1/2} = 0.03 r_0^2 / \bar{D} \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{D} = 0.03 r_0^2 / t_{1/2} \quad (3)$$

The value of pore diffusion coefficient \bar{D} are 4.25 and $4.23 (\times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1})$ which indicates that intra-particle diffusion coefficient was only rate controlling step⁶. The mass transfer analysis for the adsorption of dyes on coconut hard shell powder (CHSP) was carried out at various temperature (20, 30, 40 °C) by using the Mckay *et al.* equation⁷ :

$$\ln \left(\frac{C_t}{C_0} - \frac{1}{1 + mK} \right) = \ln \frac{mK}{1 + mK} - \frac{1 + mK}{mK} \beta_s S_s t \quad (4)$$

where C_0 is the initial adsorbate concentration, C_t is the adsorbate concentration after time t , m is mass of adsorbent per unit volume, K is the Langmuir constant obtained by multiplying Q^0 and b , β_s is mass transfer coefficient, $(3.26 \text{ and } 3.27) \times 10^{-6} S_s$ is the outer surface area of adsorbent per unit volume. This results also supported the proposition that the intra-particle diffusion is the rate controlling step.

The percentage of adsorption increases in the temperature range 20 to 40 °C at concentration 5 mg L^{-1} and pH 10.2 for crystal violet and 10.5 for malachite green. Equilibrium time for 20, 30 and 40 °C were found 100 and 90 min respectively for crystal violet and malachite

Table 1. Adsorption kinetics, thermodynamic parameters and Langmuir constants for crystal violet and malachite green at different temperatures

Parameter	Temperature (°C)		
	20	30	40
Crystal violet :			
$k_{ad} (\text{min}^{-1}) 10^{-2}$	3.42	4.03	4.65
$k_p (\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1/2})$	3.80	3.98	4.01
$-\Delta G^\circ (\text{kcal mol}^{-1})$	0.13	0.19	0.24
$\Delta H^\circ (\text{cal mol}^{-1})$	-	2.7887	2.6865
$\Delta S^\circ (\text{cal mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1})$	-	9.3249	9.4933
$Q^0 (\text{mg/g})$	0.704	0.829	0.860
$b (\text{mg}^{-1})$	0.744	0.941	1.860
R_L	1.18×10^{-1}	9.60×10^{-2}	6.73×10^{-2}
Malachite green :			
$k_{ad} (\text{min}^{-1}) 10^{-2}$	3.07	3.87	4.02
$k_p (\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1/2})$	4.3	5.2	1.8
$-\Delta G^\circ (\text{kcal mol}^{-1})$	0.14	0.19	0.25
$\Delta H^\circ (\text{cal mol}^{-1})$	-	2.4472	2.2024
$\Delta S^\circ (\text{cal mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1})$	-	8.2658	7.8957
$Q^0 (\text{mg/g})$	1.579	1.580	1.601
$b (\text{mg}^{-1})$	0.817	1.032	1.170
R_L	1.09×10^{-1}	8.83×10^{-2}	7.84×10^{-2}

Fig. 1. Langmuir isotherm plot for adsorption of malachite green (m.g) and crystal violet (c.v) on coconut hard shell powder at different temperatures.

green. The results reveal endothermic nature of the adsorption. In the present investigation Langmuir isotherm has been found to suit well for explaining the adsorption process.

The linear plots of C_e/q_e vs C_e at different temperatures (Fig. 1) suggest the applicability of Langmuir isotherm for the present system. The value of Q^0 and b at different temperature were determined from the slopes and intercepts of respective plots and are presented in Table 1.

Adsorption of both the dyes increase with increase of pH as shown in Fig. 2.

Conclusion :

Thus the coconut hard shell powder (CHSP) was found to be a very effective. Sorbent for the efficient removal of malachite green and crystal violet from waste water. Thermodynamics studies also confirmed that the process was spontaneous and endothermic. The fitness of the adsorption data into Langmuir isotherm also confirmed that the monolayer formation of the adsorbate layer took place. The optimum pH for the removal of malachite green and crystal violet were 10.5 and 10.2 respectively.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the removal of malachite green and crystal violet.

References

1. G. Mckay, *J. Chem. Tech. Biotechnol.*, 1982, 32, 750; R. A. Davies, J. K. Hartmut and M. M. Climens, *Chem. Eng.*, 1973, 73, 130; Ram Chandra, *J. Environ. Bil.*, 2001, 22, 23; G. Karthiagan, Anithapius and G. Alagumuthu, *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 2002, 9, 397; V. K. Gupta, D. Mohan, S. Sharma and M. Sharma, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 2000, 35, 2097; T. Robinsoh, G. Mc Mullun, R. Marchant and P. Nigam, *Bioresource Technol.*, 2001, 77, 247; Fug and T. Viraraghavan, *Water Qual. Res. J. Canada*, 2000, 35, 95; Fu Yuzhu and T. Viraraghavan, *Water SA*, 2003, 29, 465; G. S. Gupta, G. Prasad, K. K. Pandey and V. N. Singh, *Water Air Soil Pollut.*, 1988, 37, 13; R. I. Grim, "Clay Mineralogy", McGraw Hill Book Co, Inc, New York, 1968.
2. S. Legergreen, K. Bil and S. Svenska, *Handle*, 24, 1988 as cited by Trimdi *et al.*, *J. European Polymer*, 1973, 9, 525.
3. V. J. P. Ports, G. Mckay and J. J. Healy, *Water Res.*, 1976, 10, 1061.
4. W. J. Weber (Jr.) and J. C. Morris, *J. Sanit Eng., Div. Am. Civ. Eng.*, 1964, 90, 79.
5. F. Healferrich, "Ion Exchange", McGraw Hill Book Co., Inc, New York, 1963.
6. G. Mckay, M. S. Otterburan and A. G. Sweeney, *Water Res.*, 1981, 15, 327.
7. G. Mckay, M. S. Otterburan and A. G. Sweeney, *Water Res.*, 1980, 14, 15.